

Can a bot book that hotel for you? A survey of e-commerce web services for Austrian and German tourism

Umutcan Şimşek¹ and Dieter Fensel¹

University of Innsbruck, 6020 Innsbruck, Austria,
firstname.lastname@sti2.at,
WWW home page: <https://sti2.at>

Abstract. E-commerce of tourism services has already been an indispensable part of the tourism industry. Given the recent developments in Artificial Intelligence, particularly in conversational AI technology, it is not hard to see that the Intelligent Personal Assistants like Amazon Alexa and Google Assistant will be major channels for booking hotel rooms or buying tickets for events. The web services that serve such tourism services are statically integrated into these AI applications in the current situation. Such a manual approach would not be comprehensive and scalable, assuming a high fragmentation and heterogeneity of services and service providers. Web services should be described semantically to enable automation, so intelligent applications can select correct web services and guide their users to reach their goals. In this paper, we provide a review of the web services for e-commerce in tourism, in order to identify (a) to what extent tourism services are bookable online (b) what is the level of fragmentation among the e-commerce web services. We provide the results based on the Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) in Austria and Tourism Marketing Organizations (TMOs) in Germany.

Keywords: semantic technologies, e-commerce, web services, schema.org

1 Introduction

The visibility and scalable consumption of tourism-related content and data have already gone beyond academic interest and found industrial traction. Particularly with the introduction of schema.org, content and data publishers have utilized semantic technologies for purposes like Search Engine Optimization to improve their online visibility. Several analyses are showing that the usage of semantic annotations (especially with schema.org) in tourism has been increasing over recent years [5, 1, 7]. The most recent one shows that only in Austria, 60% of the Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) publish semantic annotations of content and data to some extent. The web resources consist of not only content and data, but also services. Naturally, the more heterogeneous and larger in number the services are, the harder it becomes for applications

that provide direct booking to consume them automatically. Therefore, similar to the content and data, services must also be semantically annotated to enable automated agents. As the first step for this endeavor, we provide a survey to answer two questions: (a) *to what extent can tourism services be booked online?* We aim to answer this question to see the level of online bookability of tourism services. There are many services published on DMO's websites, but are they directly bookable online? (b) *what is the heterogeneity of e-commerce web services?* The main motivation for using semantic technologies is to make many heterogeneous services available for automated consumption. We aim to answer this question to find out if semantic technologies are necessary at all, or the number of providers is so small and centralized that they can be easily integrated into the applications.

To conduct the survey, we focus on Destination Management Organizations (DMOs) in Austria and Tourism Marketing Organizations (TMOs) in Germany at different levels, namely state, regional, and city. The primary reason for surveying these organizations is that they aggregate different services and typically provide direct online booking. We analyze the marketing organizations for three main types of services: accommodation, event, and offer bundles/experiences. In the remainder of the paper, we will introduce our survey methodology (Section 2). We will then provide a survey of the selected subjects in terms of the e-commerce solution providers they use (Section 3). In Section 4, we will mention similar surveys in the literature. Section 5 concludes the survey with a summary of the results and discussion about the lessons learned as well as future directions.

2 Survey Methodology

We have examined a total of 83 subjects in Austria¹. Only the subjects from Salzburg, Tyrol, and Vienna have been considered since these three states generate approximately 70% overnight stays [6]. Similarly, we have selected 99 subjects from Germany². The sample represents all German states, emphasizing those that attract the most overnight stays, such as Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hessen, Lower Saxony, North Rhine-Westphalia, and Schleswig-Holstein. Like the Austrian subjects, these states provide 70% of the overnight stays [10]. We have reviewed each subject in the accommodation, event, and offer bundles/experiences sectors.

- **Accommodation:** Booking of overnight stays in lodging businesses.
- **Event:** Purchase of tickets for events.
- **Offer Bundle / Experience:** Bundles of different offers (e.g. an accommodation and an event or a tour). These are usually packages with a flat-rate.

¹ List compiled from <https://tourismusverbaende.at/>.

² We selected state, regional and, city-level marketing organizations who are members of the Association of German Tourism Marketing Organizations (DTV). See <https://www.deuschertourismusverband.de/verband/mitglieder.html>.

We have followed the steps below for each subject while conducting the survey:

1. Visit their website.
2. Check the active areas on the website (e.g. accommodation booking engine, event search, holiday package search) for information about the IT solution provider for e-commerce.
3. Check the privacy policy and imprint. These sections usually contain information regarding the third-parties with which the subject shares information. Those third parties usually include the IT solution providers for e-commerce.
4. If none of the above steps are conclusive to determine the IT solution providers, we inspect the source code and the network communication. The requests and responses as well as resource URIs usually contain information regarding the IT solution provider who provides the web service.

A solution provider is only considered for a subject if the service is directly bookable on the subject’s website or redirects to a website/platform dedicated to the subject. For example, if a DMO lists the events in a region but does not provide direct ticketing via a booking engine, the solution provider for event booking services is put under *Other/Non-Bookable* category. We give detailed discussions of the Other/Non-Bookable category for each service type in the survey results (Section 3.2).

3 Survey of E-Commerce Web Services for Tourism

In this section, we first give an overview of the different IT solution providers discovered by the survey and then detailed results per service type for each country³.

3.1 Web Service Providers at a Glance

The survey identified the usage of web services from a variety of IT solution providers in Austria and Germany (Table 1). Some of them cover multiple sectors and market their products as *destination management software*. For example, companies like feratel and TOMAS provide services for the e-commerce of rooms for lodging businesses, events, and holiday packages.

As a result of our survey, we identified the following IT solution providers that provide web services for e-commerce of certain touristic services (i.e. accommodation, event, offer bundle/experience): booking.com⁴, bookingkit⁵, buenoi⁶,

³ The raw survey results can be found online: <https://tinyurl.com/u3ahezz>

⁴ booking.com

⁵ <https://bookingkit.net>

⁶ <https://buenoi.com>

CapCorn⁷, elements⁸, eventim⁹, eventjet¹⁰, eventris¹¹, feratel¹², HRS¹³, IMS¹⁴, INCERT¹⁵, infomax¹⁶, In-house, miadi¹⁷, oeticket¹⁸, peaksolution¹⁹, reservix²⁰, Regiondo²¹, SECRA²², seekda²³, ticket2go²⁴, Ticket Regional²⁵, Ticket Service²⁶, TOMAS²⁷, TTG²⁸, vibus²⁹

Sector	IT Solution Provider
Accommodation	booking.com, buenoi, CapCorn, elements, feratel, HRS, IMS, SECRA, seekda, TOMAS, TTG
Event	bookingkit, eventim, eventjet, eventris, feratel, infomax, INCERT, In-house, miadi, oeticket, reservix, SECRA, Ticket Regional, Ticket Service, ticket2go, TOMAS, vibus
Offer Bundle/Experience	bookingkit, elements, feratel, HRS, In-house, peaksolution, Regiondo, TOMAS

Table 1. IT solution providers for e-commerce in tourism in Austria and Germany

Some of the subjects use aggregators like peaksolution as a more holistic e-commerce solution since they have integrations to many other IT solution providers, including some of the ones in this survey (e.g., feratel). Alongside web services with a custom integration, many IT solution providers offer exter-

⁷ <https://capcorn.at>

⁸ <https://elements.at>

⁹ <https://eventim.de>

¹⁰ <https://eventjet.at>

¹¹ <https://eventris.ch>

¹² <https://feratel.com>

¹³ <https://www.ds-destinationsolutions.com>

¹⁴ <http://www.ims-vienna.com/destination-management/>

¹⁵ <https://incert.at>

¹⁶ <https://www.infomax-online.de/imxeventmanager>

¹⁷ <http://info.miadi.net/de/miadi/organizer/>

¹⁸ <https://oeticket.at>

¹⁹ <https://www.peaksolution.com>

²⁰ <https://reservix.de>

²¹ <https://pro.regiondo.com/>

²² <https://secra.de>

²³ <https://kognitiv.com>

²⁴ <https://ticket2go.de/>

²⁵ <https://www.ticket-regional.de/>

²⁶ <https://www.derticket-service.de/home/>

²⁷ <https://tomas.travel>

²⁸ <https://ttg.at>

²⁹ <https://vibus.de/>

nal hosting of a DMO/TMO’s services. These are still directly booked on the DMO/TMO side; however, they are sold over a generic interface provided by the IT solution provider and linked from DMO/TMO’s website.

3.2 Survey Results

In this section, we give the survey results for each service type in Austria and Germany. The results are given from three perspectives: (1) the absolute number of subjects (#) using the given IT solution provider³⁰, (2) the percentage of each IT solution provider for a given domain (%), and (3) the percentage of each IT solution provider among the subjects that provide e-commerce of the given service (% (*)).

Austria All Austrian DMOs that were subject to the survey (see Section 2 for the selection process) offer e-commerce of accommodation on their websites. There are 10 different IT solution providers used by the DMOs to enable the e-commerce of accommodation services. feratel is the most widespread solution provider in Austria for accommodation, with about 80%. They are followed by HRS and CapCorn (Table 2).

Table 2. E-commerce web service providers for accommodation in Austria

	#	%	% (*)
booking.com	1	1.2	1.2
buenoi	1	1.2	1.2
CapCorn	4	4.82	4.82
elements	1	1.2	1.2
feratel	64	77.11	77.11
HRS	7	8.43	8.43
IMS	1	1.2	1.2
seekda	2	2.41	2.41
TOMAS	1	1.2	1.2
TTG	1	1.2	1.2
Other/Non-Bookable	0	0	0
Total	83	100	
Total (*)	83		100

For events, the situation does not look as promising as the accommodation services. We have found only 4 DMOs that offer online bookable events on their website. The unbookable events lead by 95%. However, among the non-bookable events, there is a lot to unpack. All DMOs had some listing of events, but there were some caveats:

³⁰ Total (*) represents the total number of subjects that provide e-commerce of the given service type.

- events were not bookable at all or
- events were bookable through external means and
- the external means can be via a ticketing service, phone or email

For example, many DMOs use feratel to list events and provide price information and links to various events' websites. However, they are not directly bookable on DMOs online. Nevertheless, there are 4 different service providers identified. Table 3 summarizes the results.

Table 3. E-commerce web service providers for event in Austria

	#	%	% (*)
eventjet	1	1.20	25
feratel	1	1.20	25
INCERT	1	1.20	25
oeticket	1	1.20	25
Other/Non-Bookable	79	95.20	-
Total	83	100	
Total (*)	4		100

We found 19 DMOs providing means to book offer bundles directly on their websites. feratel has about 80% of the share among the service providers. Still, a large majority of all DMOs (about 80%) do not provide any direct booking options on their websites. However, this is a similar situation to the events. Many of them have listings of offer bundles; however, they can only be booked either through an inquiry form on the DMO's website or directly on a hotel's website.

Table 4. E-commerce web service providers for offer bundles/experiences in Austria

	#	%	% (*)
elements	1	1.20	5.56
feratel	15	18.07	77.78
peaksolution	1	1.20	5.56
Regiondo	1	1.20	5.56
TOMAS	1	1.20	5.56
Other/Non-Bookable	64	77.11	-
Total	83	100	
Total (*)	18		100

Germany Similar to Austria, the majority of German Tourism Marketing Organizations (about 94%) selected for the survey (see Section 2) provide booking of accommodation services on their websites. All subjects have some listing of lodging businesses, but visitors are redirected to individual hotels' websites in

some cases. There are 5 different providers for this service type in Germany. TOMAS provides the majority of the booking engines in Germany for our subjects while feratel and HRS follow closely (Table 5).

Table 5. E-commerce web service providers for accommodation in Germany

	#	%	% (*)
booking.com	2	2.02	2.15
feratel	25	25.25	26.88
HRS	20	20.20	21.51
SECRA	1	1.01	1.08
TOMAS	45	45.45	48.39
Other/Non-Bookable	6	6.06	-
Total	99	100	
Total (*)	93		100

Events are more bookable in Germany than they are in Austria. We found a total of 26 TMOs that provide event bookings distributed among 13 different IT solution providers (Table 6). Reservix is used by 22% of the marketing organizations that provide e-commerce of events, followed by TOMAS. In addition to the third-party IT solution providers, 2 marketing organizations provide in-house developed solutions integrated with their Content Management Systems. There are still 73 TMOs with non-bookable events. All marketing organizations present events to some extent, similar to Austrian DMOs, but they also have the same caveats when it comes to booking.

Table 6. E-commerce web service providers for event in Germany

	#	%	% (*)
bookingkit	2	2.02	7.41
eventim	2	2.02	7.41
eventris	1	1.01	3.70
infomax	1	1.01	3.70
In-house	2	2.02	7.41
miadi	1	1.01	3.70
reservix	6	6.06	22.22
SECRA	2	2.02	7.41
Ticket Regional	1	1.01	3.70
Ticket Service	2	2.02	7.41
TOMAS	4	4.04	14.81
ticket2go	1	1.01	3.70
vibus	1	1.01	3.70
Other/Non-Bookable	73	73.74	-
Total	99	100	
Total (*)	27		100

We identified 30 German marketing organizations in our survey that provide online booking of offer bundles (Table 7). Among those, 20 of them use TOMAS as their booking solution, followed by feratel. There are still two-thirds of the subjects whose offer bundles are not bookable on their websites. The pattern we observed in Austria also emerges here. Many marketing organizations do have offer listings; however, they are typically bookable through different channels.

Table 7. E-commerce web service providers for offer bundles/experiences in Germany

	#	%	% (*)
bookingkit	1	1.01	3.33
feratel	6	6.06	20.00
HRS	1	1.01	3.33
In-house	1	1.01	3.33
Regiondo	1	1.01	3.33
TOMAS	20	20.20	66.67
Other/Non-Bookable	69	69.70	-
Total	99	100	
Total (*)	29		100

The survey results show interesting findings regarding the bookability and heterogeneity of touristic services in their e-commerce. We discuss these findings in Section 5.

4 Related Work

There are many surveys regarding the general adoption of ICT and e-commerce in tourism, but not with this level of detail and focus on IT solution providers. For instance, the survey in [2] focuses on the development of e-tourism in Greece in terms of ICT adoption. As for surveys specific to e-commerce, comprehensive work has been done by [3] to better understand the performance of e-commerce in tourism better. The survey in [4] examines the factors affecting the adoption of e-commerce solutions in Taiwan, while the survey in [8] measures the e-commerce adoption in several African countries. In a related direction, a survey on the usage of Web 2.0 and Web 3.0 technologies in e-marketing in Austria has been conducted in [11]. The usage of semantic technologies, particularly schema.org annotations by tourism service providers, have been analyzed in [5] and later in [1]. Another recent survey [7], analyzed the usage of semantic technologies among Austrian DMOs categorized under different topics.

To the best of our knowledge, our survey is the only one regarding the IT solution providers for e-commerce in tourism. It gives a good overview of the landscape of web services that can be annotated to enable automated consumption of web services.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

The web is built on three pillars, namely content, data, and services. As discussed in the paper, there is a significant amount of effort towards the semantic annotation of content and data; however, services are also needed to be semantically annotated to achieve truly scalable e-commerce. We have surveyed DMOs in Austria and TMOs in Germany for the IT solution providers they use for e-commerce of different services. Before concluding our work, we would like to visit the questions we posed at the beginning:

What is the bookability of the tourism services online? We found out that both in Germany and Austria, accommodation services are mostly bookable via DMOs online. For events and offer bundles, the scene is a bit different. Although almost all subjects had event listings and bundled offers, they were not bookable directly on their websites. In some cases, individual events had their own ticketing channels. Offer bundles mostly provided inquiry forms.

What is the heterogeneity of e-commerce web services? We found 27 different IT solution providers (1 for every 7 subjects) between accommodation, event, and offer bundle service types. For accommodation bookings, the heterogeneity is relatively low, considering that only three providers (i.e., feratel, HRS, and TOMAS) cover most subjects. However, we also found out that several subjects have links to individual hotels for online booking. Given the large volume, this would increase heterogeneity significantly. Meanwhile, we found 17 (1 for every 10 subjects) different IT solution providers for event ticketing services. When the external booking engines for individual events are included, the heterogeneity is again significantly increased.

One important observation we made is that there are a lot of local IT solution providers. For example, feratel, an Austrian company, is dominating the Austrian DMOs while TOMAS is very widespread among German marketing organizations. This situation indicates that if we extend our survey to different countries and service types, it is likely that the number of different solution providers may rise.

Under the light of these findings, we can conclude that semantic annotation of services is likely to improve the scalability of applications since integrating so many different IT solution providers manually into an e-tourism application would require significant centralized effort. This service integration challenge is currently addressed by Online Travel Agencies (OTAs), at least for accommodation services. OTAs integrate individual services statically in their applications. Although their centralized aggregation of services addresses issues like heterogeneity, they also eat up revenues of individual service providers. The semantic annotation of e-commerce web services first at the DMO/TMO level, then at a larger scale for individual service providers, would improve their scalable integration and consumption and prevent their revenues from flowing to OTAs. Additionally, smaller service providers not working with booking engines but

channels like inquiry forms can also utilize semantic annotations to improve their bookability (see below).

Now the ultimate question is: what would be a way for IT solution providers to annotate their APIs semantically, so the effort of discovery and integration of their services into applications is significantly reduced? There are many lightweight approaches for annotating web services [12]. Given the success schema.org had for annotating content and data, it would be a natural first step to use it for annotating services too. schema.org provides an action subset for describing actions that can be taken on entities. There are some academic efforts to restrict and enrich the action vocabulary to annotate web services³¹ [9]. Such actions can explicitly describe what "booking" means, in terms of required input and expected outputs and their constraints. Moreover, actions can be linked together, allowing an application to consume follow-up actions automatically.

One thing we should not ignore is the potential lying in the DMOs and TMOs. Many of their services go under the "Other/Non-Bookable" category. Many events and offer bundles are actionable, even though not via a web service that directly books the desired service. For example, the inquiry forms for offer bundles can be annotated with a "search action," where the form fields are mapped to the action's input description. Although this would not enable a direct booking, it can still help an application understand the inquiry form and automatically guide the user. This would help eliminate the heterogeneity of different inquiry systems and still improve the scalability despite not completing the service booking. Listing 1 shows an action annotation for an offer bundle inquiry from DMO Zell am See-Kaprun. This annotation can be embedded to the web page where the offer is presented just like any other schema.org annotation in JSON-LD format. An application can process this action annotation to guide the user to inquiry for the given offer without having an integration to the DMO Zell am See-Kaprun's website.

In future work, we would like to expand the survey to different countries and service types to have an even better picture of the landscape of e-commerce web service for tourism. We want to provide guidelines for straightforward annotation of actions, may it be a booking engine or just an inquiry form. We will develop generic applications such as an Alexa Skill that processes action annotations without having integrations to dozens of marketing organizations to demonstrate the benefit of semantically annotating e-commerce web services.

³¹ <https://wasa.cc>

```

{
  "@context": "https://schema.org/",
  "@type": "SearchAction",
  "object": {
    "@type": "LodgingReservation",
    "checkInTime-input": "required",
    "checkOutTime-input": "required",
    "numAdults": "required",
    "numChildren": "optional",
    "reservationFor": {
      "@type": "LodgingBusiness",
      "location": {
        "@type": "Place",
        "name": "optional"
      },
      "amenityFeature": {
        "@type": "LocationFeatureSpecification",
        "name-input": "required"
      },
      "starRating": {
        "@type": "Rating",
        "ratingValue-input": "required"
      }
    }
  },
  "makesOffer":
  ↪ "https://zellamsee-kaprun.com/de/unterkuenfte/angebote/anfrage?id=136194",
  "underName": {
    "@type": "Person",
    "givenName-input": "required",
    "lastName-input": "required",
    "address-input": "required"
  }
}

```

Listing 1: An annotated offer bundle inquiry form from DMO Zell am See-Kaprun

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